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PROPOSAL FOR THE ORGANISATIONAL STRUCTURE AND PROCESSES OF THE SUNRISE LARGE SCALE INITIATIVE

Solar Energy for a Circular Economy

Deliverable D4.1

Proposal for the organisational structure and processes of the SUNRISE large scale initiative

WP4. Governance and processes

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report, prepared in close collaboration with Energy-X, defines structure and processes for governing the SUNERGY large-scale research initiative (LSERI). Following an analysis of the governance schemes of existing Flagships and partnerships in H2020, the planned instruments in the context of HE are explored and clear recommendations for launching a LSERI are put forward that form the basis for D4.2, terms of reference.

The analysis of the governance structure of running Flagships and partnerships has revealed five key elements for the governance of a future LSERI. First, it is strongly recommended that the coordinator acts as a moderator and brings professional management skills. Second, decision-making processes and precise roles of the different boards have to be clear from the start. Third, strategic decisions for future research routes are to be made on the basis of sound scientific evidence to assure quality and impact. Fourth, the innovation routes and intellectual property (IP) procedures must be well defined from the start. Fifth, a general assembly and ethics board, in combination with a professional dissemination strategy, are important for good governance.

Missions and partnerships represent the two possible options for a dedicated SUNERGY LSERI in HE. Missions rely on a strong bottom-up approach to engage citizens and the society. Five missions will be launched in 2021 and SUNERGY could have links with three of them. However, to build an LSERI on missions is not recommended due to risks of fragmentation and low impact.

The other possibility are partnerships. Amongst the three different types of partnerships in HE (co-funded, co-programmed and institutionalized), **we recommend the co-programmed public private partnership (cPPP) instrument for a SUNERGY LSERI**. The flexibility of the cPPP allows including both programmatic and bottom-up components under a single governance terms of reference framework with a program board of mandated experts that are personally responsible for assuring quality and impact facilitating rapid progress, without transfer of authority from the member states (MS) and EC.

In collaboration with ENERGY-X, a first proposal for such a partnership was elaborated: “*3FCM: Fossil-free fuels, chemicals and materials for a circular economy*”. While current prospective HE public-private partnerships focus on improvements on the demand side, the 3FCM proposes a pipeline of high impact technologies that boost efficiency on the supply side with sunlight-to-products and fuels conversion from atmospheric CO₂. When vigorously pursued, this will enable full decoupling of economic growth from the utilization of resources at the local, regional, national and European levels with the supply of renewables for a sustainable resilient growing economy by 2050.

Following these recommendations a fully operational SUNERGY partnership can be structured in less than four years with a stage 1 initiation period of 1-2 years and a stage 2 ramp-up phase. Discussions around the partnerships in HE are ongoing and will be closely followed by the SUNERGY initiative.

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D4.1.

1. SCOPE OF THE DELIVERABLE D4.1 “Proposal for the organisational structure and processes of the SUNRISE large scale initiative”

D4.1 is one of the two deliverables of the Work Package (WP) 4 “Governance and processes” of the SUNRISE CSA. The scope of this WP is to establish the organisational structure and the related operating and decision processes of the future Large Scale European Research and Innovation Initiative (LSERI). Those shall ensure an effective scientific leadership and governance structure, taking into account the lessons and best practices learned from the existing Flagships and other LSERI such as partnerships. This WP is structured into three tasks and two deliverables:

- Task T4.1 (M1-M2): Analyse the governance structure of running Flagships and other European large scale initiatives ;
- Task T4.2 (M3-M8): Developing the organisational structure and processes of the future LSERI;
- Task T4.3 (M9-M12): Set-up the organisational structure and processes of the LSERI.

The original aim of D4.1 was: “*Proposal for the organisational structure and processes of the SUNRISE large scale initiative*”. It is related to Tasks T4.1 and T4.2. Two facts led to an adaptation of D4.1 compared to the original plan:

- 1) **Flagship instrument**: this instrument no longer exists in Horizon Europe;
- 2) **Merging of SUNRISE and ENERGY-X consortia**: SUNRISE and ENERGY-X, were both granted a CSA under the call FETFLAG-01-2018 and share common challenges and objectives. They agreed in August 2019 to merge at the end of the two CSAs (in March 2020) and to launch a new initiative, SUNERGY (see Appendix 5.2 for a brief description of SUNERGY), and to join efforts to pave the way towards a Large Scale European Research and Innovation Initiative (LSERI) based on SUNERGY vision and challenges.

The first point led to the adaptation of D4.1 with the idea to explore possibilities and propose scenarios to have a LSERI based on SUNRISE (and now SUNERGY) fitting into the landscape of Horizon Europe. Several options were explored, mainly related to missions and partnerships, and actions were launched in this sense in the past months. In particular, a first draft for a common partnership proposal called “*Fossil free fuels, chemicals and materials for a circular economy (3FCM)*” was jointly prepared by the SUNRISE and ENERGY-X (see Appendix 5.5) and was brought to the attention of the partnerships programme committee in June 2019. With already an established list of partnerships discussed between the European Commission (EC), the Member States and Associated Countries (MS & AC) to be launched at the start of Horizon Europe in 2021, such an additional partnership can be discussed for the next round of partnerships that could be launched in 2024. With that perspective in mind, a tentative scenario and timeline is presented in section 4 of the present document.

Regarding the second key fact mentioned above, *i.e.* the merging of SUNRISE and ENERGY-X consortia, the governance scheme and scenarios for both ENERGY-X and SUNRISE beyond the two current CSAs will both fall under the new initiative, SUNERGY. They are thus prepared in common between the groups in charge of governance in the two CSAs. Further information on

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SUNERGY, its current organization, challenges and objectives is given in section 3. More precisely, to work on governance schemes and tentative scenarios, the CSA joined efforts in the following way:

- Teleconference meetings joining the teams in charge of governance in both CSAs are regularly organized (approx. monthly) and jointly since September 2019;
- A physical meeting gathering representatives of both CSAs was jointly organized on October 22 at Roissy Charles de Gaulle Airport to work on governance schemes on the so-called short-, mid- and long term scenarios. Further details on these tentative scenarios and the outcomes of this meeting are given in section 4 and in the Appendix 5.3.

The present document is structured as follows. In **section 2**, the analysis of the governance structure of running flagships and other European large scale initiatives is detailed. **Section 3** will detail the new context for the future of SUNRISE with the creation of SUNERGY and present the actions that led to the merging plus the new organization and joint work led for building the future of SUNERGY. In **section 4**, the different scenarios envisioned for the future of SUNERGY on the short-, mid- and long-term are presented together with some indication of the proposed organization. Section 5 explains the partners responsibilities in the relevant Tasks T4.1 and T4.2 of the SUNRISE CSA related to this deliverable. It also presents the organization for these Tasks and different steps that led to building common scenarios presented in section 4 and how the work was organized jointly with the governance team of the ENERGY-X CSA. Finally, various documents mentioned in the present text can be found in the **Appendixes**.

As a final general remark, it turns out that there are still ongoing discussions with the European Commission (EC), the Member States and Associated Countries (MS & AC) and the SUNRISE, ENERGY-X and thus SUNERGY communities around some options mentioned in the present document. In particular, SUNERGY is structuring the community both at the European and national levels with dedicated events to discuss its vision, roadmap, governance and blueprint.

An additional governance workshop was thus organized on 20 February 2020 at DECHEMA in Frankfurt, with representatives of the teams in charge of the governance work packages in ENERGY-X and SUNRISE. The workshop aimed at discussing and if needed refining the governance schemes and to ensure alignment for the two CSAs and to prepare the future terms of references.

Thus and if needed, an updating on the scenarios, the governance schemes and thus to this deliverable will be made at the end of the CSA.

2. ANALYSIS OF THE GOVERNANCE STRUCTURE OF RUNNING FLAGSHIPS AND OTHER EUROPEAN LARGE SCALE R&I INITIATIVES

This section summarizes the results of Task 4.1 of the SUNRISE CSA (lead Forschung Zentrum Jülich). There is a similar task in the ENERGY-X CSA. The main outcomes of the ENERGY-X analysis is presented in the deliverable D5.1 “*SWOT analysis of existing governance models*” (lead DECHEMA) and a brief outline was also discussed during the SUNRISE and ENERGY-X governance meeting (Roissy, 22 October 2019, see minutes in section 5.2).

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In the case of the SUNRISE CSA, at first, the governance structures of the current FET flagships, which will continue as co-funded European Partnerships in HE, were analysed and compared: *i.e.* the Graphene, Human Brain and Quantum Flagships. Next, we extended our analysis to existing European large scale R&I initiatives with a private component, including the recently launched Battery 2030+ initiative as well as two different types of public-private partnership (PPP), namely the SPIRE co-programmed public private partnership (cPPP) and the FCH joint undertaking (JU). The governance schemes of these different flagships and partnerships are presented in Appendix 5.1 of the present document.

In all governance schemes for the running Flagships (Appendixes 5.1 a to c), the directorate plays the central role and together with different boards decisions for *e.g.* budget or strategic scientific directions are made. Since we found many differences in the governance structures we decided to search the pros and cons in direct contact with involved people.

Thus, in a second step, interviews with different members of the three running flagship initiatives were performed to get insights in learnings, findings, dos and don'ts regarding the various governance and organisational structures. Interview partners have been:

- Prof. Katrin Amunts - Scientific Research Director of the Human Brain Flagship and sub-program leader (SP 2 "Human Brain Data"),
- Prof. Tommaso Calarco – Coordinator of the Quantum Support Action of the Quantum Flagship.
- Prof. Max Lemme – Scientific secretary of the Strategic Advisory Council and former leader of the Partnering Division of the Graphene Flagship.

The main findings from the interviews relevant for the future SUNERGY LSERI are summarized below.

In all interviews, it was found that a General Assembly is one of the most important bodies in large scale research programs. Participants with different roles in the projects *e.g.* from the management team, from scientific advisory boards, from the stakeholder boards *et cetera*, share information, discuss strategic routes, agree on budget plans, view the latest research results and keep each other updated and in touch. This is highly important for the transparency in large projects and large initiatives.

An Ethics Board in combination with a professional dissemination strategy is a must for large scale initiatives. Since the research content is of very high public relevance and interest, the results and the focus strategy of the research route of large scale projects must be communicated in a professional way, such that society can follow *e.g.* the decisions made. The Ethics Board in parallel has to debate about the research route and the alignment between the needs and wishes from the public.

Clear decision-making processes and roles of the boards must be defined from the beginning as terms of reference. The processes should be transparent, understandable and explicit for the involved people in the project, such that discussions about the decision-making processes during the running initiatives are avoided.

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Innovation routes and IP issues must be defined from the beginning. Since there will be industrial partners involved in large-scale research initiatives or industrial partners should get on-board during the running project, both academia and industry stakeholders must clear views about the IP strategy. Furthermore, it is very much appreciated (not only for society) if there is an exploitation plan of the research results, which can be a payback of investments made *e.g.* by tax payers. Structures which deal with innovation and IP issues should be visible in the governance.

Strategic decisions for future research routes must be made on the basis of scientific expert's opinions. Therefore, one option is to build scientific strategy working groups which make the scientific strategic decisions on a common basis. This guarantees that all relevant scientists speak with one voice and conflict of interests are levelled out. An independent moderator for decision-making processes in the working groups is helpful to find best solutions. The outcomes and decisions of the different working groups can be presented to all partners and stakeholders and validated during the general assembly.

One of the strong hints in all interviews was that the coordinator should be independent in large scale research initiatives. It means that, the coordinator and with him the management of the project (*i.e.* members of an executive board) should induce *e.g.* budget distribution decisions on the basis of advice from a strong scientific advisory board. The coordinator should act as a moderator and should have no vested interest. Regarding that fact, the role of the coordinator and the management in the project is to set up and guarantee tools and processes, so that the best strategic decisions can be made for the needs from society and on the basis of the results from the science. In addition, it is highly recommended that the coordinator brings professional management skills in the project. Conflict of interests in decision-making processes must be avoided, which should be guaranteed by the coordinator.

Finally, the voice from society should be involved from the beginning. This helps to focus the research on the relevant needs of the public. A society board, in which *e.g.* people with sociology background or people from the public sectors are involved, can be integrated in the governance.

Regarding the **Battery 2030+ initiative**, it comprises three main bodies: the general assembly, an executive board and an advisory board. The **general assembly** is the ultimate decision-making body. It includes the project coordinator and the deputy project coordinator and one representative of each of the 17 members of the consortium which are leaders in their respective countries in the field of batteries. The **executive board** is the body responsible for the proper execution and implementation of the decisions of the general assembly. It is also in charge of monitoring the progress of the initiative. Finally, there is also an **advisory board** composed of European and national organizations. It plays the role of providing input to run the initiative as well as help aligning its results with expectations of the different communities involved (academic, industrial, member states and associated countries and society).

Presently, in the so-called “ramp-up phase”, the Battery 2030+ initiative is supported by a coordination and support action (CSA) which runs for a period of 3 years. Related to this, are also several open competitive calls - Research and Innovation Actions (RIA) and Innovation Actions (IA) - which are in-line with the roadmap of Battery 2030+. All selected projects are linked between them and to the CSA in the sense that they must conclude a written collaboration agreement with

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the CSA and other projects selected. Thus, they contribute to the common activities of the CSA and more globally to the Battery 2030+ initiative. Such schemes ensure that all projects are part of the global initiative, and not disconnected projects working separately. The results and outcomes of the RIA and IA projects will also contribute in updating the roadmap of the initiative. Such an organization with an “umbrella” CSA complemented by a set of different and connected open calls appears quite efficient to run a global large-scale initiative pursuing a global vision. It ensures that the two following key aspects are met:

- (i) with the CSA: to maintain and update a global vision and roadmap for the Battery 2030+ initiative, in close coordination with the European actors from academia, industry and society and the EC, MS & ACs;
- (ii) with the set RIA and IA open calls: to implement the roadmap of the initiative with open competitive calls complying with the rules of Horizon Europe, including openness, but also contributing to the global initiative via an agreement of cooperation with the CSA and with the other projects.

Such a coordination and cooperation scheme can be extended to the national level via cooperation of the global initiative with national actors including national funding agencies.

Regarding the analysis of the **governance schemes of partnerships**, we focused on SPIRE¹ and FCH-JU² that were implemented under Horizon 2020. The governance schemes of these two PPPs are presented in Appendix 5.1.d (SPIRE) and 5.1.e (FCH-JU). Generally speaking, PPPs are joint initiatives of the European Commission and actors of the private sector to support the research and innovation in domains of strategic importance to the economy and competitiveness of the European Union or to address key societal challenges, whenever these cannot be efficiently addressed using the other instruments of the framework programme. In H2020, PPPs are functioning either as contractual public-private partnerships (cPPPs) or as Joint Technology Initiatives, JTIs (also called Joint Undertakings, JU). SPIRE is one example of the first type (cPPP), whereas FCH-JU is a JTI.

A cPPP in H2020 will be a **co-programmed European partnership in HE**. The activities of a cPPP are implemented and operated in different parts of H2020 with open calls and thus follow the rules of the framework programme. In the case of SPIRE, taken here as an example, the governance structure is composed of three blocks (see Appendix 5.1.d):

- The **partnership board** is the central board connecting the public and private partners of SPIRE;
- The **European Commission** as the public partner;
- The **European Association A.SPIRE**, an aisbl representing the private partners of SPIRE.

The roles of **A.SPIRE** are multifold. It first acts as an advisory body to the partnership board by discussing priorities relevant to SPIRE and elaborating a roadmap and a strategic research agenda (SRA) based on which calls topics are proposed for the work programmes of H2020. It also participates in the operational management of the partnership with the A.SPIRE office supporting the executive director and the partnership board of SPIRE in this task. Finally, A.SPIRE also

¹ Sustainable Process Industry through Resource & energy Efficiency (SPIRE) : <https://www.spire2030.eu/intro>

² Fuels Cells & Hydrogen Joint Undertaking (FCH-JU) : <https://fch.europa.eu/page/governance>

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ensures an implementation role by forming consortia to apply to open H2020 calls of interest to SPIRE. A.SPIRE has several governing and advisory boards. The board of (elected) directors represents the 8 various industry sectors involved³. It manages and prepares the consolidated work programme of A.SPIRE. The Industrial Research and Innovation Advisory Group (IRIAG) assists the board of directors by contributing to the elaboration of the SRA and of the call topics proposed to the SPIRE partnership board. Finally, the A.SPIRE General Assembly is the representation of all SPIRE members and validates the overall strategy of A.SPIRE.

The **partnership board** is the body associating the public and private (represented by IRIAG) stakeholders of SPIRE. It is chaired by an EC representative and co-chaired by the IRIAG chair. The partnership board has a strategic and advisory role to the EC and the initiative by discussing priorities and call topics based on the SPIRE SRA. It also ensures monitoring progress of the overall partnership. Finally, the **EC** has a decision-making role by developing the work programmes and publishing open calls of interest to SPIRE based on the SPRE SRA.

In a recent report on cPPPs⁴, this governance structure was favorably evaluated. Several shortcomings were nevertheless noted, in particular a lack of transparency of the management processes and the roles and involvement of stakeholders in cPPPs as well as a lack of openness. Other noted shortcomings were the insufficient involvement of SMEs as well as an unbalanced regional coverage of the European Union with a lesser representation of EU-13 countries⁵.

FCH-JU is one the 7 JTIs currently operating in H2020. JTIs are institutionalized partnerships governed by Articles 185 or 187 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU)⁶. JTIs are long-term initiatives (up to 10 years) which aim at integrating national and European research programmes in a given field of strategic importance for European industry and competitiveness. JTIs elaborate their own research agenda and multi-annual work programmes and thus launch their own open calls and award funding. Members of JTIs are the European Commission, Member & Associated States, a not-for-profit industry led-association. SMEs, academia (universities and RTOs) can also participate in JTIs. JTIs will continue as Institutionalised European Partnerships in HE.

The governance scheme of the FCH-JU includes **two executive bodies**, the **governing board** and the **executive director assisted by the programme office**, and **three advisory bodies**, the **scientific committee**, the **states representatives group** and the **stakeholder forum**. The **governing board** is the main decision-making body of the FCH JU and has the overall responsibility for its operation. All three stakeholders are represented in the governing board of the FCH-JU, namely Hydrogen Europe (industry grouping referred to as IG in the governance scheme), the EC and the Hydrogen Europe Research (RG in the governance scheme) representing the academia involved. The **Executive Director** is the legal representative of the FCH-JU. He is

³ Namely cement, ceramics, chemicals, engineering, non-ferrous metals, minerals, steel, water, see <https://www.spire2030.eu/spire/the-association>

⁴ Mid-term review of the contractual Public Private Partnerships (cPPPs) under Horizon H2020. Report of the independent Expert Group (European Commission 2017).

⁵ EU-13 countries : 13 european countries which joined the EU since 2004 : Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Poland, Romania, Slovakia and Slovenia.

⁶ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/summary/glossary/joint_undertaking.html

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assisted by the **Programme Office** and both are in charge of the day-to-day management of the Joint Undertaking. Regarding the advisory bodies, the **Scientific Committee** is an independent advisory body to the Governing Board. The members reflect a balanced representation of world-class experts from academia, industry, SMEs, non-governmental organizations and regulatory bodies. The **States Representatives Group (SRG)** consists of one representative of each MS and AC. The SRG has an advising role to the Governing Board. Its members act also as an interface between the FCH JU and the relevant stakeholders within their respective countries. The **Stakeholder Forum** plays the role of a general assembly and gathers representatives of all stakeholders involved in the Joint Undertaking. The governance scheme of the six other JTIs follow a similar scheme.

Overall, this governance scheme was evaluated as effective⁷. Some concerns noted by the evaluators are about the limited role and impact of the advisory groups on the executive bodies and therefore on the main strategic decisions of the FCH-JU. The interactions between the advisory and executive bodies should be improved, the governance structure itself being judged as satisfactory. It is in particular key to strengthen the role of the SRG in order to ensure a better alignment of national priorities with that of the JTI. In another report⁸, experts also suggested not to limit the role of the SRG only to an advisory role in order to reinforce the weight of MS & AC in the decisions, *e.g.* by participating in the governing board. As for cPPPs, it was pointed that the participation of SMEs and EU-13 countries could be improved.

The above-discussed two PPPs operate under H2020. In Horizon Europe where the landscape of partnerships will evolve with a simplified and rationalized landscape of partnerships where openness and transparency are better addressed. Therefore, a future SUNERGY LSERI as a partnership, which would operate under Horizon Europe, should be considered in this new landscape. This is discussed in more details in section 4.3 of the present document.

Finally, the result of this analysis was shared during a governance session of the SUNRISE stakeholder workshop held on 17-18 June 2019 in Brussels. The session began with an introduction by the work package leader on the analysis of existing governance models. Then a discussion followed between panellists representing different stakeholders involved in LSERI:

- Jean-François Buggenhout | DG Connect, European Commission
- Lars Klüver | Danish Board of Technology Foundation
- Paulina Styczeń | Department of Innovation and Development of the Poland's Ministry of Science and Higher Education
- Andreas Förster | DECHEMA
- Marcel Hoek | Dutch Research Council (NWO)

⁷ Commission Staff Working Document : Interim Evaluation of the Joint Undertakings operating under the Horizon 2020 (European Commission 2017).

⁸ Final report by the ERAC Ad-hoc working group on partnerships on the recommendations on increasing the efficiency of implementation of partnerships (european research area and innovation committee, 2018).

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- Max Lemme | Scientific Secretary of the Strategic Advisory Council and former leader of the Graphene Flagship Partnering Division

The session was organized with a list of questions to the panellists on different topics followed by open questions from the audience. The topics addressed covered the future for SUNRISE in the new context of Horizon Europe and its new instruments (missions, partnerships), the cooperation with ENERGY-X, what to learn from best practices in the governance of LSERIs, the role of EC and industry in LSERIs. Several recommendations were given by the panellists with a strong focus on the cooperation with ENERGY-X. This is addressed in the next section. More details on this session can be found in the minutes of this SUNRISE stakeholder workshop.

3. UPDATE ON THE CSA, THE CONTEXT AND LAUNCH OF SUNERGY

The SUNRISE CSA, launched on March 1st 2019 for a duration of one year, was one of the 6 projects granted in the frame of the call FETFLAG-01-2018. Besides SUNRISE, another CSA was selected under the same sub-area “*Energy, Environment and Climate change: Radically new Energy Production, Conversion and Storage devices and systems*”: ENERGY-X (www.energy-x.eu).

ENERGY-X is coordinated by the Danish technical university. It gathers a total of 13 partners from academia, RTOs and industry. ENERGY-X aims at developing technologies to replace fossil resources for the future European energy mix as well for the European chemical industry by converting renewable power (*e.g.* photovoltaic, wind) under chemical form, either as a fuel of base chemical for the chemical industry. To do so, one core activity of ENERGY-X is the development of a new generation of catalysts with improved performances, durability and composition as compared to the current state of the art. This goes together with novel integrated conversion approaches to reach technologies that can be upscaled in an economically viable energy system. To do so, ENERGY-X has an interdisciplinary approach for academic research with cross-fertilization with industry. To demonstrate the feasibility of the approaches developed in ENERGY-X, two demonstrator projects are planned, one for the manufacturing of carbon-neutral aviation fuels and the second decentralized production of fertilizers with zero-CO₂ footprint.

SUNRISE and ENERGY-X have several aspects in common. First of all, they aim both at solving the following three grand challenges:

- Storage of renewable energies as liquid fuels,
- Production of basic chemicals for the industry and agriculture without fossil resources,
- Negative CO₂ emission technologies.

to be achieved by using abundant and ubiquitous molecules (H₂O, N₂, CO₂) as feedstock and renewable energy sources (*e.g.* sunlight, wind), *i.e.* resources abundant in Europe and with an overarching circular economy approach.

To solve these grand challenges, both communities SUNRISE and ENERGY-X explore different technological routes with different TRL levels and which can be summarized as follows:

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- **Conversion of renewable power to a chemical form (fuels and chemicals)** via electrochemical and thermochemical processes. It is also referred to in the literature as Power-to-X;
- **Direct conversion of solar energy to a chemical form (fuels and chemicals)** using a photoelectrochemical, biohybrid or biological approach.

ENERGY-X is mainly focused on the above-mentioned Power-to-X routes, whilst SUNRISE, besides exploring electrochemical processes, has also a strong focus on the direct conversion approaches.

Finally, SUNRISE and ENERGY-X also have common partners and supporters. Overall, the CSAs gather a total of 30 partners (from academia, industry, national and European networks and alliances) from 14 different countries : Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United-Kingdom. When taking into account the supporters, *i.e.* the organizations that expressed interest via a letter of support, this amounts to total community of approx. 300 organizations from academia, industry (approx. 50 companies so far), NGOs, governmental and local authorities from more than 25 countries across Europe and beyond. This community is meant to develop and strengthen in the future, one objective being to reinforce the participation of the industry in view of the future LSERI.

Building on these common aspects and synergies, SUNRISE and ENERGY-X maintained regular contacts at different levels in the CSAs. In particular, the need to join efforts was in fact realized very early in view of building a common future in the new context of Horizon Europe, to be a stronger community and thus to have more impact. One of the first actions launched jointly was to elaborate a partnership pre-proposal as an option for a future LSERI gathering SUNRISE and ENERGY-X. This joint pre-proposal entitled « *Fossil free fuels, chemicals and materials for a circular economy (3FCM)* » was proposed in the context of the discussions between the EC and the member states for future partnerships in Horizon Europe (see section 4.3 and appendix 5.5 for more details). The action was led in SUNRISE by the team in charge of the work package WP4 on governance. The representatives of the MS and ACs represented in the two CSAs and involved in the discussions in Brussels around new partnerships were contacted for supporting this partnership proposal. While the possibilities for having a new partnership in 2021 are very limited as there is already an established list of candidate partnerships discussed by the EC and MS & AC, upon favourable evaluation of the SUNRISE and Energy-X CSAs, and provided ample private support can be mobilised, the path to a future SUNERGY partnership can open, up. One important option to be further explored would be to have such a 3FCM launched in 2024 in a second wave of new partnerships of Horizon Europe. Other common actions between SUNRISE and ENERGY-X included participating and contributing to the stakeholder's workshops organized by each CSA.

Shortly after this common partnership proposal, the two consortia decided to merge at the end of the two CSAs to form a new and single initiative aiming at having a LSERI. This was announced at the Europacat 2019 conference (18-23 august 2019) during a dedicated session with participants from both CSAs. The new initiative is called "**SUNERGY** : *fossil-free fuels and chemicals for a circular economy*". Thus in March 2020, when the two CSAs SUNRISE and ENERGY-X have ended, the whole community will be gathered under the umbrella of the SUNERGY initiative. From

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an operational point of view, there will be a temporary governance structure, functioning to keep the community gathered and active until a new contractual frame is launched under H2020 or Horizon Europe and to pave the way towards a future LSERI. The envisioned scenarios with their timeline are detailed in the next section.

Nevertheless, not waiting until March 2020, SUNRISE and ENERGY-X are already joining efforts on some common aspects of the future SUNERGY LSERI, including preparing a blueprint and a governance structure for SUNERGY. Regarding governance, meetings are held since September 2019 with the participation of the ENERGY-X partners in charge of the governance work package.

4. SCENARIOS FOR THE FUTURE OF SUNERGY

In order to build tentative scenarios to pave the way towards a future SUNERGY LSERI based on the 3FCM proposal, a dedicated workshop was held on 22nd of October 2019 (Roissy Charles de Gaulle Airport). It was organized by the SUNRISE WP4 with support and participation from ENERGY-X members and it gathered 13 participants, 8 from SUNRISE and 5 from ENERGY-X. The Roissy workshop aimed at providing recommendations for the governance structure for this SUNERGY LSERI as well to work on possible options to implement this LSERI and launch into action after the end of the SUNRISE and ENERGY-X CSAs. These options were considered in the new frame of Horizon Europe and its structure and instruments.

Figure 1: Tentative scenario and timeline to bridge between the two SUNRISE and ENERGY-X CSAs and a future large scale European research and innovation SUNERGY initiative.

In this process, three so-called short-, mid and long-term periods were identified:

- **Short term (2020):** this period starts at the end of the two SUNRISE and ENERGY-X CSAs with the evaluation of the results of the two projects and what they have delivered. This

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period and the outcomes of the evaluation will be critical to launch the next “ramp-up phase”.

- **Mid-term (2021-2023): “ramp-up phase”** towards a SUNERGY LSERI partnership with common coordination activities backed by several RIA (Research and Innovation Actions) and IA (Innovation Actions) open calls based on the roadmaps of SUNRISE and ENERGY-X. All the granted RIA and IA projects would conclude a collaboration agreement with SUNERGY to contribute to the activities of the whole initiative and would be subject to mid-term review and evaluation at the end by a program board of experts with mandates from the MS and the EC to assure quality and impact without transfer of authority away from the MS and EU. This period would also be dedicated to develop and strengthen the SUNERGY community (academia, industry and society) and to pave the way towards the SUNERGY partnership with the contribution of the different stakeholders.
- **Long-term (after 2024):** this corresponds to the start of a SUNERGY partnership as discussed above. Regarding the type of partnership, a co-programmed European partnership (cPPP) appears as the most adapted to the SUNERGY initiative due to its flexibility and possibility to accommodate both bottom-up and programmatic efforts with maximum synergy between the two. This type of partnership allows to have both public and private partners as well as participation of member states according a memorandum of understanding (see section 4.3 for more details).

An overview of these three periods and timeline is presented in Figure 1. The main conclusions and recommendations of the Roissy workshop for each of these periods are given below together with a proposition for a governance structure for the selected scenario.

4.1. Short-term scenario (2020): after the end of the two CSAs

Context

- *Objective:* after the end of the ENERGY-X and SUNRISE CSAs (February 2020), there is the need to define a short-term strategy and framework to support SUNERGY activities and keep the community together
- *Timing:* the short-term scenario starts *from now* (to ensure continuity after the end of the CSAs) to the start of the operations through the “*bridge funding*” (medium-term period), *i.e.* the “ramp-up phase” towards a LSERI, the main objective for the long-term period.

Main conclusions on the governance and organization for the short-term period from the Roissy governance workshop:

The working groups during this workshop identified the following aspects as key for implementing a governance and organization for this short-term period.

As a general comment, there is the need to define a lean and mean structure to prepare the ground for the post-CSA. Thus, during the remaining course of the two SUNRISE and ENERGY-X CSAs, the groups in charge of governance must join efforts and coordinate their work in proposing a common structure.

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The group identified the need to create two boards for SUNERGY, each having a balanced composition from members from SUNRISE and ENERGY-X yet ensuring a global consistency of each board in terms of composition taking into account, whenever possible, aspects such as the types of organizations, the geographical distribution of members and gender to provide an optimal embedding for gaining support from member states.

- **Scientific executive board:** this board is responsible for the operational running of SUNERGY in this intermediate period with members having different roles and tasks which can be delegated upon need (*e.g.* development of joint Manifesto, outreach to EC/advocacy...). Presently this board, already created counts 8 members, 4 from SUNRISE and 4 from ENERGY-X. These are:
 - **SUNRISE:** Prof. Huub de Groot (Leiden University, SUNRISE CSA coordinator), Dr. Frédéric Chandezon (CEA), Prof. Joanna Kargul (Warsaw University), Dr. Carina (Faber, Université Catholique de Louvain);
 - **ENERGY-X:** Prof. Jens Nørskov (DTU, ENERGY-X CSA coordinator), Prof. Bert Weckhuysen (Utrecht University), Prof. Robert Schlögl (Max Planck Society, Fritz-Haber Institute and Max Planck Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion), Prof. Gabriele Centi (European Research Institute of Catalysis).
- **Industrial board:** it was suggested to create an independent industrial board separate from the scientific executive board to be effective while at the same time working in close interaction together. The industrial board would have as a main role to bring the views of industry for the overall development and strategy of SUNERGY. It was proposed to have a board counting 7 members, 3 suggested by SUNRISE and 3 by ENERGY-X. This board would be chaired by Prof. Maximilian Fleischer (Siemens) presently involved in the SUNRISE CSA. A tentative list of the other members of this industrial board has been established by Prof. Fleischer and discussed with the scientific executive board. The identified persons are presently contacted for having their agreement to join the board.

Then these two boards will be directed by a coordinator and deputy:

- Prof. Bert Weckhuysen (Utrecht University) as the coordinator of SUNERGY;
- Dr. Frédéric Chandezon (CEA Grenoble) as the deputy coordinator of SUNERGY.

They will have the responsibility of running the overall SUNERGY initiative based on the decisions of the two boards and also to prepare the next period and in particular the implementation of the “ramp-up phase” for the mid-term period (see next section). This would include in particular:

- Preparing a coordination and support action (CSA) for coordinating the overall SUNERGY initiative during the ramp-up phase. Propositions for topics are under discussion either in the frame of H2020 or for the first work programmes of Horizon Europe;
- Coordinating the preparation of RIA and IA topics based on the SUNRISE and ENERGY-X roadmaps for the first work programmes of Horizon Europe with a group

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of members from different organizations in SUNRISE and ENERGY-X, group to be implemented;

- Coordinating the preparation of a large Innovation Action, based on a topic presently under discussion with the EC.

The coordinator and deputy will be supported by a team for day-to-day management, dissemination aspects, communication and liaison with the EC, organization of events. Presently, the persons of this support team are: Kathrine Bjeregaard-Nielsen (DTU), Elena Guarneri (DTU), Laura Lopez (ICIQ) and Anita Schneider (EERA),

Furthermore, overall this period, a regular contact will be maintained with the SUNERGY community built on the SUNRISE and ENERGY-X ones. This could be done mainly via regular information sharing on the advancement of the initiative with a SUNERGY newsletter and could be done as well on a consultation of the overall community. All this is summarized in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Proposed governance structure for the SUNERGY “after CSAs” short-term period.

4.2. Mid-term scenario (2021-2023): the “ramp-up” phase of SUNERGY

Context

This “ramp-up phase” would be the intermediate period to bridge towards a SUNERGY LSERI partnership after 2024 and not a goal *per se*.

Main conclusions on the governance and organization for the mid-term “ramp-up phase” from the Roissy governance workshop:

Further preparation for the SUNERGY LSERI without any funding was perceived as being not possible especially if this LSERI starts operating in 2024. Two options were identified to coordinate and support this intermediate period: a single follow-up coordination and supporting action (CSA) and/or an ERA-NET. A CSA appears to be a very suitable option in terms of integration at the European level with some of the key leaders in European MS & AC acting as national nodes for the

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national communities in the fields covered by SUNERGY. The duration of the project should ideally be 3 years to ensure bridging with the LSERI with a budget of a minimum 3 M€ (1 M€/year).

The coordination project should provide a number of key overarching functions for the SUNERGY community, including:

- Communication and dissemination services for SUNERGY related/initiated projects (*e.g.* organisation of an annual conference for relevant projects, newsletters, etc.);
- Community-building and networking platform for stakeholders to enlarge the scientific and industrial commitment;
- Continuation of the Scientific Board and the Industrial Board as well as installation of a Board representing the Civil Society;
- Proposal of SUNERGY topics for the HE work programmes 2023/24;
- Preparation or support of a multi-annual work programme for the SUNERGY LSERI with a series of calls; proposals for specific instruments for SMEs and start-ups could be part of this programme (liaison with the EIC);
- Updating of the Strategic Research Roadmap including the integration of the SUNRISE and ENERGY-X roadmaps into one combined SUNERGY roadmap;
- Liaison with Member State (MS) Governments and the European Commission to work on the alignment of programmes and secure MS and EU funding for the LSERI respectively; this activity shall lead to additional commitment from the MS, (by analogy to the Board of Funders of the H2020, see section 4.3 below);
- Finalisation and implementation of the Governance Structure for the LSERI; this should reflect the anticipated wide range of TRLs covered by SUNERGY actions and ensure fair and non-discriminative participation of stakeholders from all member states;
- Work on a pragmatic contractual framework for the LSERI including questions on IP management, access to research results and rules for fair compensation of academic IP
- Furthermore, the project should deliver a number of standardised tools that will be essential for quality assurance and coherency and comparability of research results. This includes the set-up of a harmonized Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) framework tailored to the needs of SUNERGY. This should reflect social aspects of the intended transformation of the energy and industry system and include forecast and predictive modelling tools to assess impacts of individual new technologies. Another key requirement is the standardisation of testing and characterisation methodologies to ensure that research results of different projects or groups are comparable (for example standardized procedures for (photo)catalyst testing). This might also include development of appropriate methodologies and could also lead to a network of central testing and characterisation facilities.

One recommendation for this coordination part is about the consortium composition. Whilst it appears clear that it will differ from the current consortia of the SUNRISE and ENERGY-X CSAs,

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it appears nevertheless essential to keep key partners to ensure a certain continuity in the overarching functions described above.

Following those conclusions, several options are presently under discussion including for a CSA call for the H2020 work programme 2020 or alternatively for the first calls of Horizon Europe. The former option is the preferred one, as it would ensure start of the project in early 2021. It received the support of several member states. If this is not retained, then the call topic could be proposed for the first work programmes of Horizon Europe, thus meaning an additional delay to start the mid-term period as the CSA could not start before at least end of 2021. The text of the CSA topic proposed is given in Appendix 5.4. Additionally, an ERA-NET could be a way to ensure a good alignment with national priorities. This is also presently under discussion.

For the implementation of the SUNERGY roadmap, this coordination part should be complemented by several research and/or innovation actions (RIA/IAs). These calls of different sizes would be launched as open competitive calls based on the priorities identified in the roadmap of SUNERGY (itself built by merging the SUNRISE and ENERGY-X roadmaps) and proposed by the SUNERGY initiative during the preparation of the work programmes of Horizon Europe in early 2020, as discussed in the previous section. The calls would follow the rules of Horizon Europe (or H2020 if there are possibilities for adding SUNERGY topics in the WPs based on remaining budget) thus ensuring a fair and open competition. All the granted projects would have to conclude a written collaboration agreement with the SUNERGY CSA and the other selected RIA and IA projects, and both the midterm review and the end evaluation of these projects will be performed by the SUNERGY board operating under a mandate from the MS, AC and EC to prevent separation of authority from responsibility. Keeping the authority over the end result with the MS, AC and EC will ensure that both the RIA bottom-up components and the IA programmatic components contribute to the activities of the global SUNERGY in synergy. It also appeared during this Roissy governance meeting that, besides regular small projects, having a very large project (budget minimum 100 M€) in this intermediate period could help in gathering a significant number of European actors around a core project, giving further visibility to the SUNERGY initiative vis-à-vis the European Commission, the Member States and the society. All this portfolio of European RIA and IA projects could also be complemented by national funded projects.

Figure 3: Proposed governance structure for the SUNERGY “ramp-up phase” mid-term period.

An overview of a governance scheme following this option is presented in **Figure 3**. In this scheme, the coordination of SUNERGY is ensured by a CSA, possibly complemented by an ERA-NET to ensure coordination and alignment with national funding. The SUNERGY board, including the scientific and industrial boards, launched during the short-term period could be continued, complemented by a societal component. Such a board would have an advisory role both to the SUNERGY coordination and to the European Commission and Member States. Alternatively, these boards could be merged in a single strategic advisory board.

It should also be emphasized that there might a delay between the start of the CSA (depending when a call is published) and some of the RIA and IA projects, *i.e.* the “ramp-up” phase could start even if the CSA has not started using the organization structure and processes established during the short-term period (Figure 2).

An alternative option to the above-discussed scheme - where coordination and research and innovation aspects of the SUNERGY are done using dedicated separate instruments of H2020 and Horizon Europe - would be to merge the two aspects in a single large project with a budget of 100-200 M€ and a period allowing to bridge with the LSERI. The community development could be achieved with an extended dissemination component. As dissemination is mandatory anyway, it could focus on dedicated community building, triggering new calls, and anything else that a CSA could contribute, with the added advantage that the difficult task of securing 80% private funding is leading and puts the primate with serving society (*i.e.* the market) over serving science (*i.e.* academic knowledge gathering). Presently no such instrument exists in H2020 and Horizon Europe. Such option has the main advantage of being an extremely visible single action for the SUNERGY initiative both at the European and National levels, it bridges into action and it gives freedom for programmatic steering and limited redundancy. The main drawback is a lack of flexibility and the openness. For such a call, there could only be one single project and thus one consortium selected.

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It doesn't seem reasonable to embark every interested member of the broad SUNERGY community (presently around 300+ members) in such a project. Thus for the non-selected members, this would block for them possibilities to join European SUNERGY-like projects. There is a high risk then that some partners "leave" the community whilst it needs to be reinforced and strengthened especially in view of launching for the long-term period a SUNERGY LSERI. Thus, such a scheme appear as non-optimal to ensure the required openness of SUNERGY during this key "ramp-up" phase to embark all the community in the future LSERI.

4.3. Long-term scenario (after 2024): the SUNERGY Large Scale European Research and Innovation Initiative

Context

This corresponds to the start of the SUNERGY LSERI. During the course of the SUNRISE and ENERGY-X CSAs, several options were considered including the **mission** instrument to be implemented in Horizon Europe and **partnerships**. One key aspect was to have an option and instrument that avoids fragmenting the SUNERGY initiative into several existing projects and communities. This would lead to the loss of momentum and efficiency and weaken the global initiative.

- **Figure 4:** From challenges to missions. From *Mission-oriented research and innovation in the European Union : a problem-solving approach to fuel innovation-led growth*, Mariana Mazzucato (2018).

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Missions are a new instrument to be implemented in the frame of Horizon Europe. They are based on a problem-solving approach around a so-called **Mission Area** to fuel research and innovation around a global challenge of broad societal interest, with specific and measurable targets to be achieved with a portfolio of research and innovation measures within a given period. There is a strong emphasis on public engagement. Thus, a mission will be structured with a portfolio of R&I projects falling in a work programme proposed to the EC by a **Mission Board** for each mission area (see Figure 4). Each mission board is composed of world-class experts appointed by EC following an expression of interest and should reflect the diversity of disciplines and expertise relevant to the Mission Area⁹. SUNRISE and ENERGY-X launched a joint action to have experts applying to some of the mission boards for missions areas relevant to both initiatives (see below). More details on the concept of missions and some insights on their governance can be found in several reports^{10,11}.

Five Missions Areas were selected for the first round of missions, to be launched in 2021 at the start of Horizon Europe:

- *Adaptation to climate change, including societal transformation;*
- *Cancer;*
- *Ocean, seas, coastal and inland waters;*
- *Climate neutral and smart cities;*
- *Soil health and food*⁹.

Although the exact outline of the mission will be defined by the mission boards, some details on their scope were given in the call for applications for the members of the mission boards with a list of keywords¹². It appears that SUNERGY has potential connections to a various extent with 3 mission areas: “*Adaptation to climate change, including societal transformation*”, “*Climate neutral and smart cities*” and “*Soil health and food*”. It thus appeared that Missions were not an optimal solution as a long-term scenario for a SUNERGY LSERI due to the risk of fragmentation already discussed above, unless a new mission built on the SUNERGY vision is launched in the future. Nevertheless, connections between the SUNERGY LSERI and the above mentioned relevant missions areas will be initiated in the mid-term “ramp-up” phase. Additionally, in the future if a new round of Missions is launched, there is the possibility of having a mission area corresponding to the SUNERGY vision. There is presently no guaranty, as the EC and the MS will first evaluate the achievements and the impact of the five missions before launching new ones.

⁹ Call for applications for the selection of the mission boards : <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/help-us-shape-horizon-europe-mission>

¹⁰ Missions : Mission-oriented research and innovation in the European Union : a problem-solving approach to fuel innovation-led growth, Mariana Mazzucato (2018). https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/mazzucato_report_2018.pdf

¹¹ Governing Missions in the European Union, Mariana Mazzucato (2019). https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/research_and_innovation/contact/documents/ec_rtd_mazzucato-report-issue2_072019.pdf

¹² Call for applications for the selection of the mission boards : <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/help-us-shape-horizon-europe-mission>

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Regarding **partnerships**, there is a new approach in Horizon Europe as compared to H2020. This is summarized in Figure 5. The general approach is to have a simplified and rationalized landscape of objective-driven and impact focussed partnerships in support to of the EU policy objectives. Partnerships are instruments to be used whenever other instruments of the framework programme are not sufficient to give the required impact.

In this new HE landscape, three types of partnerships will co-exist;

- **Co-programmed European Partnerships:** between the Commission, MS & AC and private and/or public partners. Such partnerships will be based on memoranda of understanding and/or contractual arrangements. Compared to H2020, they are similar to the cPPP model, such as for the SPIRE partnership (see section 2). Co-programmed partnerships in Horizon Europe follow a roadmap and a strategic research and innovation agenda (SRA). The contribution of the EU will be implemented via open calls in the Horizon Europe Work programmes based on propositions of topics following the partnership roadmap and SRA. This ensures openness of the initiative. The partners implement their commitments (*i.e.* activities and contributions) under their own responsibility, following pre-defined objectives. The progress of the initiative is monitored using key performance indicators. Such a co-programmed partnership can be supplemented by coordination and support actions. Co-programmed is a flexible type of partnership in its setting-up and its implementation, in terms of composition of partners, its objectives and activities that can evolve as the partnership goes. Commitments are based on common and agreed efforts between the partners and not legally binding. It is adapted to initiatives addressing large communities with a broad range of disciplines as is the case for SUNERGY.

It should be emphasized that compared to the previous cPPPs of H2020 which was used for partnerships with industry, **co-programmed partnerships in Horizon Europe will allow to have both Member States and Industry**. The participation of Member States implies the signature of Memoranda of Understanding between MS representatives and the Commissioner, the main objective being to align national priorities of participating MS with the partnership roadmap. The exact details on the type of activities from participating states are still under discussion. Ongoing discussions indicate that this could be done via national and/or transnational calls, via the research and innovation activities of national research organizations or via other activities at the national and regional levels, provided that these activities contribute to the achievement of the roadmap and the strategic research agenda of the overall partnership.

- **Co-funded European Partnerships** are based on a joint programme agreed by the partners. These partnerships associate EC with MS and AC with research funders and other public authorities at the core of the consortium. Funding of the partnership is ensured by a blending of EU and national public (*e.g.* national funding agencies) and/or other R&I funding sources. The funding rate of the EU is 30 % and up to 70 % in justified cases and the typical duration will be 5 to 7 years. The core partners are mainly national programme owners and managers form MS & AC. The implementation is ensured based on annual work programmes with

rules agreed by the partners. In H2020, FET Flagships, ERA-NET and EJP cofunds were co-funded partnerships.

- **Institutionalised European Partnerships:** they include Public-to-Public partnerships (P2P) where the EU participates in R&I funding programmes that are undertaken by a number of EU countries. They are based on article 185 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU). They can also be public-private partnerships established under Article 187 TFEU, such as joint undertakings (as FCH-JU) or EIT Knowledge and Innovation Communities (KICs). Such institutionalised partnerships are best suited for partnerships addressing long-term challenges and priorities with a stable consortium of core partners bringing substantial contributions. They call for establishing dedicating entities for their implementation thus meaning a substantial effort to set-up the partnership and imply legal binding commitments. The flexibility is rather limited as changing objectives, partners require amendment to the legislation.

Figure 5: Approach to partnerships in Horizon Europe compared to H2020. From <https://www.era-learn.eu/partnerships-in-a-nutshell/r-i-partnerships/transition-to-horizon-europe>.

As already discussed above, a proposition was jointly prepared by the SUNRISE and ENERGY-X CSAs and communities and proposed as a topic for the first round of new partnerships to be launched at the beginning of Horizon Europe, in 2021: “*Fossil free fuels, chemicals and materials for a circular economy (3FCM)*” (see Appendix 5.5). Unfortunately, it could not be selected as there was already a list of new partnerships proposals established and under discussion between the EC and the MC & ACs. One option proposed for the 3FCM proposal was to join existing communities proposing a candidate partnership having connections with SUNERGY, especially

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“Circular and climate neutral industry” (follow-up of the SPIRE, co-programmed partnership) or “Clean hydrogen” (follow-up of FCH-JU, institutionalized partnership). If there are clear connections between these two proposals and SUNERGY, these do not cover all aspects of the SUNERGY vision as they mostly focus on the demand side (applications) whilst SUNERGY focus is on the supply side, *i.e.* fossil-free fuels and base chemicals. Thus, there is a risk of only incremental impact due to the fragmentation and gaps in the vision of SUNERGY when joining established communities compared to the option of having a SUNERGY dedicated partnership. This option for a SUNERGY LSERI was thus considered as not being a suitable one.

To conclude, **the scenario which is proposed for a SUNERGY LSERI on the long-term is to have a dedicated partnership based on the “Fossil free fuels, chemicals and materials for a circular economy (3FCM)” proposal** (Appendix 5.5). This will be rediscussed in the coming years with the MS & AC and the EC upon favourable review of the outcomes of the SUNRISE and Energy-X CSAs.

Key aspects that must be addressed in the governance structure of the future partnerships are the shortcomings identified in the mid-term evaluations of cPPPs¹³ and Joint Undertakings¹⁴ and already discussed in section 2. This includes having clear and transparent processes of the different bodies and stakeholders in the governance structure of the partnership. It is in particular important to establish a strong connection between the advisory and executive bodies so that the former can impact the decisions of the latter. In the future SUNERGY partnership, industry should have a very active role both in the governance and in the implementation. Such a partnership is indeed expected to have a leveraging effect with industrial investments, in particular in promoting high technology readiness levels (TRLs) of the initiative. Besides large companies, a special focus should be given on embarking SMEs. It will be also important to ensure a balanced regional coverage of the European Union with a good representation of the EU-13 countries. In general, the governance and processes should ensure permanent openness of the initiative with the possibility of new partners to join the initiative as it goes (and open the possibility to some partners to leave), with clear participation processes and requirements. A strong emphasis must also be given to the role of MS & AC and to allow proper alignment with national priorities. One possibility would be not to limit the role of MS & AC to an advisory role but allow them to participate in the governance.

Regarding the type of partnership for the future SUNERGY LSERI, as mentioned above, co-programmed or institutionalized are suitable for public-private partnerships (Figure 5). Co-programmed is a type of partnership that is rather flexible during its implementation in terms of composition of partners of its objectives and activities and that can evolve as the partnership goes. The commitments are not legally binding but based on common and agreed efforts between the partners of the partnership. It is suited to partnerships addressing broad communities as is SUNERGY. Furthermore it allows, to have the participation of private partners **and** Member States. It requires a limited effort to set-up and implement compared to the other types of partnerships. On the other hand, institutionalized partnerships have legally binding commitments and thus require

¹³ Mid-term review of the contractual Public Private Partnerships (cPPPs) under Horizon H2020. Report of the independent Expert Group (European Commission 2017).

¹⁴ Commission Staff Working Document : Interim Evaluation of the Joint Undertakings operating under the Horizon 2020 (European Commission 2017).

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significant efforts to prepare. During its course, it shows also a limited flexibility as changing *e.g.* partners or objectives require amending the legislation.

To summarize, **it appears that the most-suited type of partnership type for a SUNERGY LSERI would be a co-programmed partnership.** It has the advantage of allowing to have both public and private partners as well as member states in the same instrument. This latter aspect thus allows to answer one of the shortcomings mentioned above with the need to align national priorities with those at the European level. The mid-term “ramp-up phase” discussed above will be dedicated to strengthen the community, in particular the participation of industry. As the contribution of Horizon Europe for a co-programmed partnership will be implemented via open calls in the work programmes of Horizon Europe, it also shows a continuity with the proposed “ramp-up phase” with its portfolio of RIA and IA projects, ensuring a certain continuity between the different phases and thus a better efficiency. This “ramp-up phase” would also be dedicated to further develop the relation with MS and their participation in the future partnership, based on the connections already established during the course of the two CSAs.

In terms of governance for a SUNERGY co-programmed partnership, the structure established for the mid-term “ramp-up phase” (Figure 3) could evolve in a structure suited for such type of partnership (see *e.g.* the example of SPIRE in Appendix 5.1.d). The EC and MS would represent the public bodies while the SUNERGY board of the “ramp-up phase” could evolve into a single programming board associating mandated expert members of the public and private stakeholders plus a funding board with representatives of EC and MS and ACs. Generally speaking, the programming board would act as the main liaison body with the public partners and the coordination and implementation part of SUNERGY. A tentative structure is displayed in Figure 6. In the SPIRE cPPP, industry established the association A.SPIRE, an aisbl representing the private partners. This option should be considered whether it is suitable in the case of SUNERGY during the short-term and “ramp-up” mid-term phase.

In the case of a cPPP, the SUNERGY governance model should be an open community structure that on the one hand allows nurturing new ideas at low TRL levels while on the other hand it can deliver on time at the higher TRL levels in a coherent manner (Figure 6). It aims to cover the hole in the Paris agreement, how to genuinely proceed towards zero and negative emission technology on the supply side, which is insufficiently covered by the existing partnerships. It is surprising that virtually all effort in the existing partnerships is on the demand side, while upstream, at the beginning of the conversion chain, the decoupling of economic growth from utilization of resources will have to be realized. In addition, direct air capture is thus far a distant promise, and currently the technology conundrum that biomass can do CO₂ assimilation but is not scalable, while human made technology is scalable but is not affordable/sustainable needs to be addressed in a thorough manner. Probably the only way forward is to go beyond the current practice of adiabatic conversion chains where losses factorize, and explore on a massive scale information in systems approaches. Since time is pressing, the only way forward is by covering the entire TRL range 0-9.

Past experience with partnerships (such as SPIRE and the flagships) has shown that

- Only bottom-up programming is insufficient to achieve rapid progress;

D4.1.

- Continued support from the member states requires a fair redistribution of resources put in by these states.

To achieve this, SUNERGY proposes for the future LSERI a governance structure where a programming board is central. In this programming board, experts with a mandate from their state have the responsibility to plan the work and perform scouting in the community for new ideas worth to be developed further. As it doesn't appear feasible to have experts mandated from all MS/ACs, the experts should reflect the geographic diversity of EU with a significant representation of EU-13 countries and they could be changed during the course of the partnership. The programming board steers the implementation towards its higher goals with a mandated program with large scale efforts at higher cost that need to be finished on time, and a bottom-up program that is bringing in the new developments. Both parts are monitored on a two-year basis. Once the expert program board has decided on a new program element to be necessary for achieving the goals, it will be presented for funding to the member states through the funding board, and the community of researchers will be asked to bring out bids.

Figure 6: Tentative governance structure for the SUNERGY co-programmed public-private-partnership cPPP partnership.

Central to the governance is graceful failure. Limited redundancy will be built in to mitigate the risk of overall failure. Every project contributing to the program is awarded for four years, and after two years the mandated experts perform mid-term evaluations, to assure quality and impact, and decide whether the work is on track. Based on this the assessment is green, which means it progresses well and a new program can be expected after the four year term, orange, which means that it is in danger and will be stopped after four years if nothing changes, or red, which means there is immediate danger and affirmative action is necessary.

Limited redundancy is actually beneficial for mitigating risk, while at the same time it also allows for improving fairness in redistribution of resources brought in by the member states. This can be

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achieved in two ways: for the mandated program, different member states can put up manufacturing infrastructure in parallel. For instance, there can be a demonstrator in France, but also in Germany, and the best elements of both will then serve to fuel a next stage development. Second, personnel performing the work will be recruited from the member state bringing in the financing, so that the resources flow back to state citizens that represent their taxpayers community.

This model is roughly based on the ESA structure, which is operational for almost 50 years and has brought Europe to the forefront of space research.

As a final remark, a governance workshop was organized on 20 February 2020 at DECHEMA in Frankfurt, with representatives of the teams in charge of the governance work packages in ENERGY-X and SUNRISE. The workshop aimed at discussing, if needed refining the governance schemes in order to ensure alignment for the two CSAs and to prepare the future terms of references to be discussed in the D4.2 deliverable. The above-discussed governance schemes were used as a starting point and any evolutions following this workshop will be described in deliverable D4.2.

5. APPENDIXES

5.1. Governance schemes of running Flagships and other European large research initiatives

5.1.a Governance structure of the graphene Flagship

5.1.b Governance structure of the Human Brain Flagship

5.1.c Governance structure of the Quantum Flagship

5.1.d Governance structure of the SPIRE PPP

5.1.e Governance structure of the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen Joint Undertaking (FCH-JU)

5.2. Brief description of the SUNERGY initiative.

Fossil-free fuels and chemicals for a circular economy

Leading the way to a climate-neutral EU by 2050

THE CHALLENGE we are facing

Running our entire world strongly depends on fossil-based energy sources and raw materials. Their intensive use over the last decades not only depleted the Earth's reservoirs, but also caused a significant increase of the carbon dioxide concentration in the atmosphere and therewith **global warming**, with tremendous consequences for ecosystems, resources and society in general. In the EU, **the energy and**

transport sector generate the major part of greenhouse gas emissions, with 54% for energy and 24% for transport-related activities in 2016. These sectors remain central for **economic growth, industrial competitiveness and quality of life**. At the same time, the electrification of society continues to grow, with the **need for efficient storage solutions**.

THE SOLUTION we are providing

By using **energy from renewable sources** (sunlight, wind) and **abundant molecules** (CO₂, water, nitrogen), we can **produce fuels and chemicals** that can contribute to stopping global warming:

Storage of renewable energy as liquid fuels

Production of fossil-free base chemicals for industry and agriculture

Technologies with a negative CO₂ footprint

THE TEAM who is working on it

We can count on a **vast base of supporters**, which continues to grow. Their work is driven and backed by key players from **academia, industry, civil society as well as governmental and local authorities** from many different sectors and based all over Europe, in the USA, Africa, and Australia.

Leadership team

Consortium partners from 14 countries

5.3. Minutes of the SUNERGY governance meeting, Roissy Charles de Gaulle Airport, 22 october 2019.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 816336

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 820444.

Minutes of the SUN-ERGY governance meeting Roissy Charles de Gaulle Airport 22 october 2019

Elena Guarneri (DTU), Kathrine Bjerregaard-Nielsen (DTU), Maximilian Fleischer (Siemens), Alexis Bazzanella (DECHEMA) and Frédéric Chandezon (CEA),

Participants:

Present:

- [SUNRISE](#): H. Bercegol (CEA), F. Chandezon (CEA), C. Faber (UCL), M. Fleischer (Siemens), H. de Groot (Leiden U.), J. Kargul (Warsaw U.), Ann Magnuson (Uppsala University), A. Schneider (EERA)
- [ENERGY-X](#): A. Bazzanella (DECHEMA), L. Bruckner (DTU), K. Bjerregaard (DTU), E. Guarneri (DTU), B. Weckhuysen (Utrecht Univ., by Skype at 10 H 00-11 H 00 and 16 H 10 – 16 H 25)

Invited: L. Klüver (Danish Tech Foundation)

Organization of the meeting:

- [SUNRISE](#): F. Chandezon (CEA, chair of the meeting), M. Fleischer (Siemens)
- [ENERGY-X](#): L. Bruckner (DTU), K. Bjerregaard (DTU)

Supplementary material:

- **20191022_SUN-ERGY_Governance_Meeting_Background_Slides.pdf**: slides presented for introducing the meeting, the context plus background material
- **DG_ENER_Lunch time conference_Agenda_Concept.pdf**: agenda of the meeting at DG ENER on October 24
- **20191022_SUN-ERGY_Governance_Meeting_Sessions_Conclusions.pdf**: slides summarizing the outcomes for the brainstorming sessions for the short-, mid- and long-term plans
- **June 2019 Partnership proposal SUNRISE-ENERGY-X.pdf**: joint SUNRISE and ENERGY-X partnership proposal “Fossil Free Fuels, Chemicals and Materials for a circular economy (3FCM)”

5.4. Proposal for a CSA topic for the mid-term “ramp-up” phase scenario.

1.1 Proposed topic for upcoming call

The proposed CSA topic is related to a proposal for the first WPs of HORIZON EUROPE of a large-scale research and innovation initiative SUNERGY on Fossil Free Fuels, Chemicals and Materials for a circular economy. It will be backed by several RIA and IA type calls within the beginning of HORIZON EUROPE that will conclude a collaboration agreement with this CSA project in pursuing common challenges within the SUNERGY roadmap. The SUNERGY initiative gathers a community of around 300 key players from academia, industry and civil society as well as governmental and local authorities. SUNERGY results from the merging of the two projects SUNRISE and ENERGY-X that were granted a CSA (March 2019 → February 2020) in the frame of the call FETFLAG-01-2018 for preparing a large scale European research and innovation initiative.

The objectives are:

- To build a strongly networked European “Fossil free” community around common goals defined in a strategic research agenda,
- To create the European ecosystem that will deliver the knowledge, technologies and open research infrastructures and testbeds necessary for the development of a world-leading knowledge based industry in Europe, leading to long-term economic, scientific and societal benefit.

The present CSA proposal falls within the scope of the fight against climate change and aims:

- at structuring/developing in the short term the European ecosystem in order to speed up technologies to move from the laboratory to industry (this would be done mainly through the IA topics of the large-scale research initiative, and also the CSA which will network and coordinate the activities and the stakeholders),
- at tackling long-term research challenges in the field (this would be done mainly through the RIA topics of the large-scale research initiative, with coordination of the research activities by the CSA).

Because of their ambition, their scale and their interdisciplinary nature, these challenges can only be realised through a long-term, coordinated and sustained effort at European level, by building on large-scale research cooperation across academia and industry and with other research initiatives at regional, national and European level, and by mobilising Europe’s best researchers around an ambitious research agenda.

Overall, this CSA together with the related selected projects of the related RIA and IA calls will be part of a ramp-up phase of the SUNERGY initiative to prepare a large scale European research and innovation initiative after the CSA, as a partnership or another instrument to be discussed and agreed together with the EC and the MS and AC.

Specific challenge

- To coordinate the research activities and the relevant stakeholders (academia and RTOs, industry, NGOs and governmental and local authorities) participating in this large-scale research and innovation initiative for the specific purpose of establishing an effective and proactive bridging pipeline between low TRL 0-3 and high TRL 7-9 and to contribute to the broader efforts in line with the EU energy strategy and the European Green Deal around the three grand challenges:
 - Storage of renewable energies as liquid fuels;
 - Production of basic chemicals for the industry and agriculture without fossil resources;
 - Negative CO₂ emission technologies.

These 3 grand challenges must be tackled/addressed by using abundant and ubiquitous molecules (H₂O, N₂, CO₂) as feedstock, renewable energy sources (e.g. sunlight, wind) and an overarching circular economy approach.

- To develop and structure (with creation and implementation of a roadmap) the European ecosystem that will deliver the knowledge, technologies and open research infrastructures and testbeds necessary for the development of a world-leading knowledge-based industry in Europe, leading to economic, scientific and societal benefits (see context below).
- To help speed up the technologies to move from the laboratory to industry with concrete prototype applications and marketable products while advancing at the same time the fundamental science basis, in order to continuously identify new applications and find better solutions for solving scientific or technology challenges.

Context

- European Green Deal;
- Links with the European Energy Research Alliance (EERA) and its joint programmes;
- SET-Plan and the key action areas renewable fuels and bioenergy, carbon capture and storage and energy efficiency for industry;
- Links with future Missions of Horizon Europe: Mission areas 1 (Adaptation to climate change including societal transformation), 4 (Climate neutral and smart cities) and 5 (Soil health and food:
 - Climate change as a geopolitical, social and economic threat;
 - Europe's high dependence on imports of climate-threatening fossil fuels as the main form of energy storage to be delivered on demand (e.g. jet fuels);
 - Limits of renewable electricity due to intermittency;
 - Storage of renewable energy fluxes as a key challenge for the ecological transition;
 - Fostering new clean manufacturing industries in the context of a circular economy;
 - Need to develop alternatives to fossil-based fuels for transportation including for aviation;
 - Need to establish a new agricultural model, rooted in decentralized, renewable based, production of inputs, in smart farming practice towards a rebalanced nitrogen-related planetary boundary.

Beyond the European Union, there are links with four out of the seven innovation challenges (ICs) of Mission Innovation, namely: Converting Sunlight IC5 (led by EU and Germany), Carbon Capture IC3; Sustainable Biofuels IC4, Clean Energy Materials IC6.

Scope :

Proposals should aim at coordinating the research activities and the relevant stakeholders (academia and RTOs, industry, NGOs and governmental and local authorities) participating in this large-scale research initiative. In particular, it is expected:

- to implement a governance structure and provide support for its governance,
- to facilitate dialogue and cooperation on crosscutting topics, to establish a communication platform,
- to consolidate a unified roadmap based on the 2 roadmaps delivered by SUNRISE and ENERGY-X CSAs (with identification of priorities) ; this roadmap may serve as an input for the preparation of Horizon Europe calls (especially Clusters « Climate, Energy and Mobility », « Digital, Industry and Space », « Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment ») as well as being inspiration for ERC projects.
- to provide a continuous revision of the roadmap according to new scientific and technological results,
- to coordinate and promote joint activities with the selected projects of the related RIA and IA calls,
- to promote the objectives of the large-scale research initiative and monitor the progress,
- to communicate and exchange on this progress and the major evolutions of the roadmap to a wide community of scientists and engineers,
- to organize outreach events (including addressing the impact of technology development on economy and society),
- to identify training and education needs,
- to identify and coordinate relevant standardisation, IPR actions, and international collaboration and help networking of respective national and international activities in the field.

It is expected that such an activity is driven by the relevant actors of the field including academia, RTOs and industry, in particular the ones gathered in the CSA actions for FET Flagships SUNRISE (<https://sunriseaction.com/>) and ENERGY-X (<https://www.energy-x.eu/>) now merged in the new initiative SUNERGY.

Note that special Grant Conditions will apply for project granted under this topic. In particular, the project partners will need to conclude a collaboration agreement with the other projects selected from the RIA and IA topics of the large-scale research initiative.

Expected impact :

- Coordinating a large scale European research and innovation initiative on storage of renewable (solar) energies in chemical form involving all relevant stakeholders and linked with relevant international, national and local programmes and initiatives;
- Building and updating a long-term SUNERGY roadmap beyond the current CSA based on the SUNRISE and ENERGY-X roadmaps;
- Facilitating cooperation and communication between the stakeholders of the initiative on cross-cutting topics;
- Developing the SUNERGY community with all relevant stakeholders (academia and RTOs, industry, NGOs and civil society) across EU;
- To strengthen the engagement of the European industrial stakeholders in particular in view of engaging in a LSRI beyond the CSA;
- Fostering the technological, economic and societal impact of the initiative and paving the way to industrial exploitation of the technologies in the field of energy, transport and climate;
- Speeding-up and increasing the positive impacts of technologies on climate change and protection of environment;
- Spreading of S&T excellence across Europe, increased awareness of European activities;
- Addressing international cooperation in particular with other relevant actions (e.g. Mission Innovation);
- Preparing a large-scale research and innovation initiative beyond the CSA, as a partnership or another instrument to be discussed and agreed together with the EC and the MS and AC.

Integration and European added value: Enhanced Europe's competitiveness on the global scale, support the development of European competitive industries and SME in the field, fostering the development of new applications, products and decrease the dependency of Europe on external resources;

Type of action: Coordination and Support Actions

Proposed starting year and duration: End of 2020 for 3-4 years

Expected contribution from the EU: 3-4 M€

5.5 Proposal for a partnership around the SUNERGY vision and challenges.

General information	
Preliminary title of the European Partnership	Fossil Free Fuels, Chemicals and Materials for a circular economy (3FCM)
Short description of the partnership	<p>Solve the following 3 grand challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Storage of renewable energies as liquid fuels; - Production of basic chemicals for the industry and agriculture without fossil resources; - Negative CO₂ emission technologies, <p>to be achieved by using abundant and ubiquitous molecules (H₂O, N₂, CO₂) as feedstock, renewable energy sources (e.g. sunlight, wind) and an overarching circular economy approach.</p>
Services directly involved	DG RTD DG ENER DG CLIMA DG MOVE DG ENV DG AGRI
Context and problem definition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate change as a geopolitical, social and economic threat • Europe's high dependence on imports of climate-threatening fossil fuels as the main form of energy storage to be delivered on demand. • Limits of renewable electricity due to intermittency • Storage of renewable energy fluxes as a key challenge for the ecological transition • Opportunity to foster new clean manufacturing industries, in the context of a circular economy. • Need to establish a new agricultural model, rooted in decentralized, renewable based, production of inputs, in smart farming practice towards a rebalanced nitrogen-related planetary boundary.
Objectives and expected impacts	<p>The overall goal of 3FCM is to provide in a clean and climate-friendly way all the value and services presently obtained from fossil resources which in addition are essentially imported from outside Europe. Although it will take at least 30 years to achieve a global ecological transition, 10 years will be sufficient to kick-start key technologies, and turn into attractive commercial activities the most advanced existing industrial processes. The 10-year objective of the 3FCM partnership is to enable the progressive displacement of fossil resources, using renewable energy to convert molecules from the environment (H₂O, N₂, CO₂) into valuable products. This grand challenge will be realised by inventing, developing, improving, engineering, socially adapting and commercially deploying devices for the provision of fuels, commodity chemicals, base chemicals and monomers for the synthesis of fertilizers, plastics, and building materials.</p> <p>On the longer term, 10-30 years, the partnership will aim at the deployment of economically viable and energy efficient negative emission technologies.</p> <p>To replace fossil stocks, we will use the same primary resources as Nature did on geological times to produce coal seams as well as oil and gas fields. Thus, 3FCM aims at using solar energy for recycling atmospheric gases, especially CO₂, the most voluminous waste of over 200 years of global economic development. The effective concentration of solar energy into chemical species may be accomplished by several conversion routes depending on location (latitude), targets (fuel, commodity chemicals, long-term storage of carbon) and technological maturity. Wind or PV electricity in temperate climates combined with electrochemistry and advanced</p>

	<p>catalysis is an open route, whereas direct sunlight conversion can operate in regions with abundant sunshine employing photoelectrochemistry, bioinspired photocatalysis or biological (biohybrid) systems. Technologies to concentrate waste or atmospheric gases, mainly CO₂ and H₂O, are also part of most strategies to be developed.</p> <p>Three key performance indicators of the viability of these technologies will be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • sober use of abundant and cheap raw materials in a circular economy approach; • maximization of the overall Energy Return On energy Invested (EROI); • minimal use of land. About this 3rd criterion, conservative estimates allow optimistic projections on the use of mostly already artificialized areas, such as industrial and commercial districts, or urban areas. <p>The technological benefits will be assessed quantitatively in a systemic approach including economic, social and environmental studies. Beyond the profit of avoided CO₂ emissions, climate science will be involved in the partnership to guide the overall development of the technologies and avoid any unintended environmental consequence.</p> <p>The 3FCM partnership will have a tremendous impact on the society, economy and the environment. On the economical and industrial side, we foresee:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced investment in CO₂-neutral energy technologies • Decrease of the carbon footprint of heavy industrial emitters • Opportunity of making economically attractive CO₂ storing materials.
Necessity test: rationale for a European Partnership	<p>The two initiatives SUNRISE and ENERGY-X have been already funded as CSAs for future FET Flagships. As the Flagship instrument will not be replicated in Horizon Europe, the support to large scale research initiatives is at stake - the domain to be covered by the 3FCM partnership is presently scattered between various instruments (including partnerships such as FCH-JU, MCSA, FET and ERC) at the detriment of a coordination of efforts. No current partnership fully addresses the challenges and expected impacts as presented above. The two initiatives are already based on strong research-industry links - a partnership would enhance Europe's competitiveness on the global scale, building on the excellence of research and leading role of Europe's chemical industry.</p>
Relevant for the following parts of Horizon Europe	<p>Pillar II 'Global Challenges and European Industrial Competitiveness'</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cluster Climate, Energy and Mobility <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cluster Digital, Industry and Space <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cluster food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment
Currently identified links with other partnership candidates /union programmes	<p>There are evident links with the following candidate partnerships:</p> <p>Climate, energy and mobility:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clean Energy Transition - Clean Hydrogen - Clean Aviation - Towards Zero-emission Road Transport - Built Environment and Construction <p>Digital industry and space:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Circular and Climate Neutral Industry <p>Similarly, there are links with the future Missions of Horizon Europe: Mission area 1 (Adaptation to climate change including societal transformation), 4 (Climate neutral and smart cities) and 5 (Soil health and food).</p> <p>Additionally, there are potential links with several of the Joint Programmes of EERA: Advanced Materials and Processes for Energy Applications (AMPEA), Bioenergy, Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS), Economic, environmental and social impacts (JP e3s), Energy Storage, Fuel Cells and Hydrogen, Photovoltaic Solar Energy, and Smart Cities At a global scale, there are links with three out the seven innovation challenges (ICs) of Mission Innovation, namely: Converting Sunlight IC5, Carbon Capture IC3; Sustainable Biofuels IC4, Clean Energy Materials IC6</p>

Does the proposed partnership build on currently active ones?	This partnership builds on two ongoing CSA actions for FET Flagships: - SUNRISE: Solar Energy for a Circular Economy (https://sunriseaction.com/) - ENERGY-X: https://www.energy-x.eu/
Expected type and composition of partners	The partnership would gather academia, research organizations and industry stakeholders, based on the still growing community of the two currently active CSAs. These communities also include NGOs, governmental and local authorities. Overall, the partnership will have all the relevant stakeholders, including end-users, to address the whole value chain. Currently, the SUNRISE and ENERGY-X communities collectively gather over 300 key players from academia, research, industry, national and European networks and alliances, funding bodies, NGOs and other stakeholders.
Contributions and commitments expected from partners	In-kind contributions (usage of research infrastructures and facilities, etc.) from academia, Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs) and industry. Industry will also participate in building exploitation strategies for securing early revenues.
Currently envisaged implementation mode(s)	<input type="checkbox"/> Co-programmed European Partnership <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Co-funded European Partnership <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutionalised European Partnership <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Article 185 <input type="checkbox"/> Article 187 <input type="checkbox"/> EIT-KIC
Justification of the implementation mode	
Proposed starting year	2021

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